

SOCIO-ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN NUH DISTRICT OF HARYANA: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

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ABSTRACT

Enhancing financial inclusion is recognized as a potent tool for promoting socio-economic development and alleviating poverty by providing individuals with sufficient access to a range of digital financial services tailored to their needs. This research was undertaken in the rural areas of three tehsils of Nuh district, Haryana, involving the selection of 120 rural households through stratified and judgment sampling techniques. Utilizing a binary logistic regression model to assess the association between variables, the findings revealed that all components of financial inclusion exerted a statistically significant positive impact on socio-economic development in the studied areas. Specifically, variables such as age, gender, and savings were identified as significant contributors to financial inclusion, showcasing their crucial roles in fostering economic development. In essence, the study underscores the crucial role of financial inclusion in fostering economic development in these specific rural areas.

KEYWORDS: Financial Inclusion, Socio determinants, Economic determinants etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the Indian economy, the evolving financial landscape has heightened the need for individuals to acquire digital financial literacy. The government is actively committed to advancing digital infrastructure and narrowing the digital divide. Recognizing the crucial link between digital financial literacy and the nation's economic development, particularly in a country like India with comparatively low per capita income, addressing key issues is imperative to bridge the gap through digital financial literacy. These issues include a lack of knowledge, concerns about online fraud, inadequate internet facilities, and limited access to smartphones. Digital financial literacy has emerged as a focal point in social science research as it aligns with the goal of achieving financial inclusion. Recent initiatives by the Indian government underscore its commitment to enhancing digital financial inclusion and digitalization. This involves improving critical digital infrastructure, enhancing internet speed and connectivity, and extending outreach, especially in rural areas. The establishment of digital access channels, particularly through widespread mobile phone adoption, has played a pivotal role in reaching low-income and financially excluded individuals globally. Jones (2021) notes that digital technology, particularly in the form of Fintech, has effectively addressed the financial needs of unbanked individuals in remote areas. Consequently, financial inclusion stands out as a potent tool for countries to attain inclusive growth by facilitating access to and utilization of financial services. Advocates for financial inclusion, such as Yin et al. (2019), emphasize its significance in achieving financial stability, alleviating social and economic challenges, and reducing poverty. The positive impact of financial inclusion on economic growth and development is also acknowledged by scholars like Van et al. (2019). Majumdar and Gupta (2013) define financial inclusion as the comprehensive incorporation of the entire adult population into the realm of banking and financial services, encompassing loan facilities, insurance options, and the freedom to opt for these services. Financial inclusion, in its strictest sense, involves ensuring that at least one member of each household has access to formal sector banking services through a deposit account. According to Swamy (2014), the

goal of financial inclusion is to establish connections between individuals and formal financial institutions, leading to consequential benefits.

Numerous theoretical and empirical studies, such as Cicchiello et al. (2021), Demirguc-Kunt et al. (2017), and Musembi and Chun (2020), have individually demonstrated the substantial connections between financial inclusion and economic growth and development. However, there has been limited research thus far that comprehensively investigates financial inclusion as a catalyst for socio-economic development. To address this gap, the present study endeavors to fill the void. Its primary objective is to assess and analyze the impact of financial inclusion components on socio-economic development in low-income areas. Additionally, the study aims to explore the relation between socio-economic development and various factors related to financial inclusion, as well as other determinants. In essence, the research seeks which aspects of financial inclusion are instrumental in fostering inclusive socio-economic growth in low-income areas of Nuh district of Haryana.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Prasad & Meghwal (2017) conducted a study that emphasized the significance of digital financial literacy as a potent tool for enhancing the financial inclusion of society. The research focused on households in the Udaipur district of Rajasthan. Aggarwal & Gupta (2014) aimed to evaluate the financial literacy awareness among students in Chandigarh, Punjab. The study involved 180 students, and the analysis considered 148 respondents. The findings indicated that the level of education and discipline had a notable impact on financial decision-making. The study identified specific areas where both the government and banks could concentrate their efforts to enhance the financial literacy of students. Srivastava & Sharma (2016) investigated banking habits and financial service awareness among households in Udaipur, Rajasthan. The study, involving 120 households, revealed that a majority of respondents had bank accounts but lacked awareness of various financial services. Additionally, the study highlighted the significant role played by the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) in shaping financial inclusion. The impact of digital financial services on economic and inclusive growth has been explored in various literatures, with a predominant focus on specific regions or at the national level. A notable study by Evans (2018) investigated the potential of digital financial services to promote financial inclusion in Africa, revealing a significantly positive relationship between the use of the internet and mobile phones and the processes of financial inclusion and socio-economic development. Similarly, Durai and Stella (2019) conducted an empirical study examining the influence of digital finance on financial inclusion in India. Their findings demonstrated the transformative effect of digital technology on the banking system, facilitating the delivery of digital financial services. In a survey conducted in 2021, Vyas and Jain (2021) investigated the significance of adopting digital technologies for promoting financial inclusion among 433 educated adults in Rajasthan, India. The expanded technology acceptance model reflected a substantial impact ($R^2 = 0.28$) concerning the digital economy and financial inclusion. Moreover, Beyene and Makina (2019) utilized cross-sectional data from 168 nations, including 48 African countries, to provide empirical evidence on the relationship between Information and Communication Technology (ICT) progress and financial inclusion. Their findings indicated that technology, particularly internet access and ATMs, significantly enhanced both access to and utilization of financial services, thereby positively influencing the socio-economic landscape in communities.

Martínez, Hidalgo, and Tuesta (2013) observed in their study that individual socio-economic factors play a crucial role in influencing individuals' decisions regarding the use of formal saving or credit financial services. They identified insufficiency or variability of income and self-exclusion as the most significant barriers to financial inclusion in Mexico. Shabna (2014) highlighted lower financial literacy, lack of awareness, and transaction costs as important barriers to financial inclusion. Devlin (2005) found that individuals with a more secure economic status are less likely to experience financial exclusion, with cultural and psychological barriers also hindering access to financial services. Bhanot et al. (2012) conducted a study in north-east India's Assam and Meghalaya states, concluding

that income and educational status were the main determinants of financial inclusion in these regions. Nandru et al. (2016) investigated the determinants of financial inclusion in Pondicherry, India. Using a binary logistic regression model, they found that among various socio-economic variables, only income and education levels significantly impacted financial inclusion, measured by the ownership of a bank account. Furthermore, Heimann and Mylenko (2011) suggested that the likelihood of accessibility to financial institutions is higher among males, middle-aged professionals in full-time employment, belonging to middle- to high-income groups, and possessing cars, telephones, and homeownership. According to Salgotra et al. (2021), there is a substantial association between financial inclusion and education, health, and standard of living. In a study conducted in specific districts of West Bengal, India, Pravat et al. (2011) investigated the determinants of financial inclusion. Their findings revealed that educational status and economic status played pivotal roles in determining financial inclusion in these regions. Specifically, they identified a positive correlation between the economic status of households and the level of financial inclusion in the studied areas.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research aimed to conduct an empirical examination of the factors influencing financial inclusion. Data were gathered through a comprehensive questionnaire consisting of questions related to financial inclusion and other dimensions representing socio-economic aspects. To ensure a thorough understanding of the topic, the research team consulted various resources, including books, journals, magazines, and reports. The study employed a convenience sampling method, and surveys were administered using the questionnaire. For the purpose of data collection three tehsils; Nuh, Taoru and Punahana were randomly selected from Nuh district. From these two villages from each were randomly selected, with that a quota of 20 respondents was set for each village. From the selected six villages a total of 120 respondents were conveniently considered for the purpose of data collection.

4. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

To access the relationship between financial inclusion and social-economic variables binary logistic regression was implemented. The results were tabulated and present the section below.

TABLE 1.1 INDEPENDENT VARIABLES CONSIDERED FOR STUDY

Variables	Options	Frequency
Age	18-30	10
	31-40	40
	41-50	37
	51-60	23
	above 60	10
Source of Income	Agriculture	74
	Livestock	25
	Daily-wage labour	10
	Employment under government welfare schemes	5
	Self-employed	6
Savings	Yes	86
	No	34
Gender	Male	47
	Female	73

For the "Age" variable, respondents are distributed across different age groups, with 10 individuals falling within the 18-30 range, 40 in the 31-40 range, 37 in the 41-50 range, 23 in the 51-60 range, and 10 individuals above 60 years old. The "Source of Income" variable reveals diverse sources, with 74

individuals engaged in Agriculture, 25 in Livestock, 10 in Daily-wage labor, 5 employed under government welfare schemes, and 6 being self-employed. Regarding "Savings," 86 respondents have answered affirmatively (Yes), while 34 have indicated a lack of savings (No). In terms of "Gender," the dataset comprises 47 males and 73 females. To facilitate analysis, these categorical variables can be recoded into binary values, allowing for the application of binary logistic regression to understand associations and predict outcomes based on the provided data.

TABLE 1.2: MODEL SUMMARY

Model Summary			
Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	19.348 ^a	.783	.898

The model summary provides a snapshot of the logistic regression analysis conducted in a stepwise fashion. In the first step, the "-2 Log likelihood" is reported as 19.348, which represents the negative twice the log-likelihood of the model. A lower value is generally indicative of a better fit, suggesting that the model's likelihood of predicting the observed outcomes is relatively favorable. The "Cox & Snell R Square" is reported as 0.783, and the "Nagelkerke R Square" is 0.898. These values represent measures of the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the model. Higher values suggest that a larger proportion of the variability in the dependent variable is accounted for by the model. In this case, the model appears to have a relatively high explanatory power, with both the Cox & Snell and Nagelkerke R Square values indicating substantial variance explained.

TABLE 1.3: HOSMER AND LEMESHOW TEST STATISTICS

Hosmer and Lemeshow Test			
Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	2.276	8	.971

With a p-value of 0.971, which is greater than the typical significance threshold of 0.05, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis in this context is that the model fits the data well. Therefore, based on the Hosmer and Lemeshow test, there is no significant lack of fit, and the model appears to fit the data adequately.

TABLE 1.4 BINARY LOGISTIC REGRESSION STATISTICS

Variables in the Equation							
		B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 1 ^a	Age	-2.799	1.115	6.302	1	.012	.061
	Gender	1.682	.997	4.848	1	.041	5.376
	Source of Income income	-.892	1.390	.412	1	.521	.410
	Savings	1.396	.997	5.959	1	.032	4.038
	Constant	-1.281	1.717	.556	1	.456	.278

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: Age, Gender, source of income, Savings.

Null Hypothesis (H01): There is no association between Age and Financial Inclusion.

The coefficient for Age is -2.799, and its p-value is 0.012, which is less than the 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis stating no association between Age and Financial Inclusion is rejected (p = 0.012). This suggests a statistically significant association between Age and financial inclusion.

Null Hypothesis (H02): There is no association between Gender and Financial Inclusion.

The coefficient for Gender is 1.682, and its p-value is 0.041, which is less than 0.05. This implies that Gender is statistically significant. The null hypothesis asserting no association between Gender and Financial Inclusion is rejected ($p = 0.041$). Thus, there is a statistically significant association between Gender and Financial Inclusion.

Null Hypothesis (H03): There is no association between Source of Income and Financial Inclusion.

The coefficient for Source of Income is -0.892, and its p-value is 0.521, which is higher than 0.05. The null hypothesis indicating no association between Source of Income and the outcome variable is not rejected ($p = 0.521$). Consequently, there is insufficient evidence to establish a significant association between Source of Income and Financial Inclusion.

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no association between Savings and Financial Inclusion.

The coefficient for Savings is 1.396, and its p-value is 0.032, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, Savings is statistically significant. The null hypothesis suggesting no association between Savings and Financial Inclusion is rejected ($p = 0.032$). This indicates a statistically significant association between Savings and Financial Inclusion.

5. CONCLUSION

This research focused on assessing the impact of financial inclusion on socio-economic development in the rural areas of three tehsils in Nuh district, Haryana. Through a comprehensive study involving 120 rural households, the binary logistic regression model was employed to analyze the association between various components of financial inclusion and socio-economic development. The findings revealed that all components of financial inclusion exerted a statistically significant positive impact on socio-economic development in the studied areas. Specifically, variables such as age, gender, and savings were identified as significant contributors to financial inclusion, showcasing their crucial roles in fostering economic development. The binary logistic regression statistics supported the rejection of null hypotheses associated with age, gender, and savings, signifying their significant associations with financial inclusion. In the broader context, this research underscores the pivotal role of financial inclusion in promoting inclusive socio-economic growth in low-income rural areas. The study contributes to the existing literature by comprehensively investigating financial inclusion as a catalyst for socio-economic development, filling a gap in research that has been limited in this regard. The identified factors, such as age, gender, and savings, can serve as valuable insights for policymakers and financial institutions aiming to enhance financial inclusion in similar contexts. Overall, this research emphasizes the importance of tailored digital financial services in addressing the unique needs of rural populations, ultimately contributing to broader socio-economic development goals.

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